

A new medical model of perioperative diagnosis and treatment for complex congenital heart disease - application of multi-modal diagnosis and treatment technology based on three-dimensional printing

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Abstract:

The diagnosis of complex congenital heart disease is challenging due to its complex anatomical structure. The existing diagnostics rely on the rich clinical experience of ultrasound doctors, radiologists and surgeons to clarify the structural malformations and spatial relationships of complex congenital heart diseases. Our research objective is to explore the role of multi-modal diagnosis and treatment system based on three-dimensional (3-D) printing technology in perioperative diagnosis, surgical treatment and postoperative evaluation of complex congenital heart disease (CHD). Especially in our country where with low diagnostic level of ultrasound and cardiac CT, can our new medical model based on 3-d printing improve the diagnosis and treatment level of complex congenital heart disease in those regions? From July 2017 to July 2019, data of 44 cases of complicated CHD (including total endocardia cushion defect, transposition of the great arteries, double outlet right ventricle, coronary artery fistula etc. 11 diseases) in Beijing and Sichuan were collected, and STL data generated by cardiac CT reconstruction were transmitted to 3-D printer. 1:1 solid heart model was printed with color partition module and myocardial and blood pool rendering technology (Figure 1). Combined with echocardiography and cardiac CT examination, preoperative diagnosis, surgical strategy development and results of surgical treatment were conducted by cardiologists, sonographers, radiologists and surgeons.

Figure 1: Figure showing a 3-D printed model of the heart in a patient with right ventricular double outlet. The picture on the right shows that the model processed by blood-pool rendering technology can more clearly show the spatial relationship within the heart and make it easier for doctors to understand disease typing.

40 patients received surgical treatment, including 30 cases of corrective surgery and 10 cases of palliative surgery. Intraoperative exploration of cardiac malformations in all patients was consistent with the 3-D printed model. Echocardiography diagnosis in 5 patients was misdiagnose from surgical exploration, with a misdiagnosis rate of 12.5%. And 2 patients' CT images didn't recognize cardiac anomalies structure, which in 3-D print model was clearly visible. The misdiagnosis rate of CT was 5%. The operation method was consistent with the preoperative reservation method. These results show that 3-D printing technology has unique

advantages in the application of complex CHD diagnosis and treatment, such as anatomical simulation and three-dimensional display of spatial relationship of heart structure, etc. (Figure 2). In regions with low diagnostic level of ultrasound and cardiac CT, complex CHD is easy to be misdiagnosed. 3D printing technology can effectively improve the diagnosis and treatment level of complicated CHD in those regions, which is worth further promotion.

Figure 2: Figure shows a 3-D printed model of a patient of mirror-image dextrocardia and with corrected transposition of great arteries. We used separate printing technique to print the patient's arterial system and left ventricle in red and the patient's venous system and right ventricle in blue.

Keywords:

Three-dimensional printing; congenital heart disease; Cardiac surgery; Cardiac Imagine

Acute SVC Obstruction Following Cardiac Surgery: Stenting vs. Surgical Intervention

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Abstract:

Acute Superior vena cava (SVC) obstruction is a rare but recognized complication following cardiac surgery that may result in significant clinical sequelae if not treated early. Transcatheter stenting is rapidly becoming the treatment of choice, considering its reduced post-procedure morbidity and faster recovery time. In early postoperative vascular lesions, primary stenting is preferred over balloon angioplasty to prevent fresh suture line disruption. In paediatric, small patient sizes, as well as the need for future vessel growth, complicate the use of stents in this group of patients. We present three cases of successful relief from severe SVC obstruction that occurred early after cardiac surgical repair. Case 1 and 2, are a 2-month-old girl and 10-month-old-boy with large perimembranous ventricular septal defect (VSD) who underwent VSD closure but was complicated by SVC tear during cannulation. Case 3 is a 35-year-old gentleman with a sinus venosus atrial septal defect, who underwent Warden procedure but developed SVC obstruction at SVC-right atrium anastomosis site. The presentation and management of these patients will be highlighted in these three cases.